

AMINO DERIVATIVES OF FERROUS IODIDE

BY SARJU PRASAD AND D. R. KRISHNAMURTY

The amino derivatives of ferrous iodide have been prepared by the action of ferrous iodide on some mono, di, secondary and tertiary amines, their properties studied and structures discussed.

The co-ordination number of iron is six, but compounds in which iron has co-ordination number less than six have also been reported in literature. Reinosuke Hara (*Chem. Abs.*, 1952, 2437^a) studied the formation of complex salts of α - and β -naphthylamine and *m*- and *p*-tolidine with ferrous sulphate. They gave inflections at approximately 1:1 and 1:2. Breuil (*Compt. rend.*, 1933, 196, 2009) prepared complex compounds of ferrous chloride and ethylenediamine, but in spite of the chelation, these were not very stable, and decomposed in air. Some double salts such as $\text{FeI}_2 \cdot 2\text{HgI}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are reported in literature, but there is no evidence to show that these contain complex ferrous ions.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the formation of compounds by treating ferrous iodide with aromatic and aliphatic amines in ether.

EXPERIMENTAL

The amine and ferrous iodide used were of B.D.H. "extra pure" quality and ether was distilled over metallic sodium.

General Method of Preparation.—A dilute ethereal solution of the amine was added to the ferrous iodide solution in ether with constant shaking till the precipitation was complete. The precipitate was filtered and washed with anhydrous ether till the washing did not produce any precipitate with ferrous iodide. It was dried at the room temperature, analysed and its properties studied. Iodine was estimated as AgI and iron as Fe_2O_3 . Two sets of experiments were carried out simultaneously. The results reported in Tables I, II and III are the average of the two values.

TABLE I
Compounds of ferrous iodide with primary amines.

Amine.	Compounds formed.	Colour.	M.P.*	% Iron.		% Iodine.		% Org. substance (by diff.).	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	Di- <i>p</i> -toluidino-FI Fe (Me.C ₆ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Dark brown	150°	10.60	10.66	48.12	48.45	41.28	40.86
<i>o</i> -Naphthylamine	Di- <i>o</i> -naphthylamino-FI Fe (C ₁₀ H ₇ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Light brown	165°	9.52	9.37	43.10	42.58	47.38	47.05
<i>β</i> -Naphthylamine	Di- <i>β</i> -naphthylamino-FI Fe (C ₁₀ H ₇ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Black	147°	9.62	9.37	42.72	42.58	47.66	47.05
<i>o</i> -Xylylidine	Di- <i>o</i> -xylylidino-FI Fe (Me ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Yellowish brown	215°	9.97	10.12	45.22	45.57	44.81	43.91
Aniline	Di-anilino-FI Fe (C ₆ H ₅ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Dark brown	140°	11.22	11.26	51.80	51.17	36.98	37.57
<i>p</i> -Phenetidine	Di- <i>p</i> -phenetidino-FI Fe (C ₇ H ₅ O.C ₆ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Grey	220°	9.54	9.56	43.36	43.45	47.10	46.99
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	Di- <i>m</i> -toluidino-FI Fe (CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Muddy	157°	10.23	10.66	47.52	48.45	42.25	40.89
<i>p</i> -Aminodimethyl-aniline	Di- <i>p</i> -aminodimethylamino-FI Fe (NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Black	210°	8.44	8.75	40.10	39.77	51.46	51.48
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	Di- <i>o</i> -toluidino-FI Fe (Me.C ₆ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Black	183°	11.23	10.66	46.96	48.45	41.80	40.89
Benzylamine	Dibenzylamino-FI Fe (C ₆ H ₅ .CH ₂ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Brown	230°	11.35	10.65	47.98	48.43	40.67	40.92
<i>o</i> -Anisidine	Di- <i>o</i> -anisidino-FI Fe (CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Brown	228°	10.71	10.04	45.24	45.63	44.06	44.33
<i>o</i> -Phenetidine	Di- <i>o</i> -phenetidino-FI Fe (C ₇ H ₅ O.C ₆ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Orange-brown	189°	9.55	9.56	43.0	43.45	47.45	45.99
<i>p</i> -Anisidine	Di- <i>p</i> -anisidino-FI Fe (CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Brown	216°	10.85	10.04	45.82	45.63	45.33	44.33
isoPropylamine	Di-iso-propylamino-FI Fe (CH ₃ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Reddish brown	180°	13.12	13.06	59.72	59.34	27.16	27.60

FI denotes ferro's iodide.

* Melts with decomposition.

TABLE II
Compounds of ferrous iodide with primary diamines.

Diamine.	Compound formed.	Colour.	*M.P.	% Iron.		% Iodine.		% Org. substance (by diff.).	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
<i>o</i> -Naphthalenediamine	<i>o</i> -Naphthalenediamino-Fe Fe [C ₁₀ H ₆ (NH ₂) ₂] ₂ I ₂	Black	140°	12.12	11.94	54.52	54.26	33.36	33.80
Dianisidine	Dianisidino-Fe Fe (CH ₃ O.NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₃) ₂ I ₂	Green	276°	10.91	10.54	48.92	47.88	40.17	41.58
Ethylenediamine	Ethylenediamino-Fe Fe (NH ₂ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Dark brown	118°	15.21	15.10	67.20	68.63	17.59	16.37
<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine	<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamino-Fe Fe [C ₆ H ₄ (NH ₂) ₂] ₂ I ₂	Black	210°	12.80	13.37	61.40	66.75	25.30	25.88
<i>o</i> -Tolidine	<i>o</i> -Tolidino-Fe Fe (CH ₃ .NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₃) ₂ I ₂	Ash colour	206°	11.20	10.70	47.95	46.62	40.85	40.68
<i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine	<i>o</i> -Phenylenediamino-Fe Fe [(NH ₂) ₂ .C ₆ H ₄] ₂ I ₂	Black	225°	13.81	13.37	60.21	60.75	26.98	25.88
Phenyldrazine	Phenyldrazino-Fe Fe (C ₆ H ₅ .NH.NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	White	155°	13.04	13.37	61.20	60.75	25.76	25.88
Benzidine	Benzidino-Fe Fe (C ₆ H ₄ .NH ₂) ₂ I ₂	Yellowish brown	219°	11.31	11.32	51.26	51.41	37.43	37.26

* Melts with decomposition.

TABLE III
Compounds of ferrous iodide with secondary and tertiary amines.

Amine.	Compound formed.	Colour.	M.P.	% Iron.		% Iodine.		% Org substance (by diff.).	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Diphenylamine	Tri-diphenylamino-Fe Fe [(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ NH] ₃ I ₂	Brown	224°	7.08	6.83	31.65	31.06	61.32	62.11
Benzylamine	Tribenzylamino-Fe Fe (C ₆ H ₅ .NH.CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₅) ₃ I ₂	Yellowish brown	256°	6.50	6.50	28.76	29.53	64.74	63.97
Ethylamine	Triethylamino-Fe Fe (C ₂ H ₅ .NH.C ₂ H ₅) ₃ I ₂	Black	213°	8.42	8.29	37.92	37.70	53.66	54.01
Di- <i>p</i> -tolylamine	Tri-di- <i>p</i> -tolylamino-Fe Fe [(CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄) ₂ NH] ₃ I ₂	Yellowish brown	222°	6.27	6.20	28.08	28.16	65.65	65.64
Dibenzylamine	Tri-dibenzylamino-Fe Fe [(C ₆ H ₅ .CH ₂) ₂ NH] ₃ I ₂	Brown	214°	5.80	6.20	28.32	28.16	65.88	65.64
Di- <i>n</i> -propylamine	Tri-di- <i>n</i> -propylamino-Fe Fe [(CH ₂ .CH ₂ .CH ₂) ₂ NH] ₃ I ₂	Yellowish brown	263°	9.32	9.11	42.57	41.39	48.11	49.49
<i>n</i> -Propylamine	Tri- <i>n</i> -propylamino-Fe Fe [(C ₃ H ₇ .NH.CH ₂ .CH ₂) ₃ I ₂	Do	239°	7.76	7.81	35.52	35.49	56.72	56.70
Tribenzylamine	Tri-tribenzylamino-Fe Fe [(C ₆ H ₅ .NH.CH ₂ .CH ₂) ₃ I ₂	Brownish black	264°	4.74	4.70	21.65	21.56	73.61	73.74
Triethylamine	Tri-triethylamino-Fe Fe [C ₂ H ₅ .CH ₂ .N] ₃ I ₂	Brown	215°	9.23	9.10	41.46	41.39	49.51	49.51
Dimethyl- <i>o</i> -toluidine	Tri-dimethyl- <i>o</i> -toluidino-Fe Fe [CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .N(CH ₃) ₂] ₃ I ₂	Yellowish brown	211°	7.83	7.81	31.98	32.50	60.19	59.69

DISCUSSION

The co-ordination number of iron in the cases studied is either two or three and therefore the effective atomic number does not assume the inert gas configuration. The compounds are stable in the dry atmosphere at room temperature, but begin to hydrolyse slowly as soon as they come in contact with moisture or when treated with sodium carbonate or sodium hydroxide solutions. The compounds formed with monoamines hydrolyse slowly at the room temperature and rapidly at higher temperatures and ferrous hydroxide is precipitated according to the following equations :

but those obtained with the diamines are more stable and hydrolyse slowly even on boiling.

On heating alone, these decompose, giving out iodine which condenses on the cooler parts of the tube. When they are heated with soda-lime, the corresponding amines separate out and condense on the cooler parts of the tube. All the compounds respond to the diazo test.

It appears that the amines attach themselves to the central atom, chelate compounds being formed in the case of diamines, which is responsible for the greater stability of these compounds. In the case of secondary and tertiary amines, three molecules are attached to the central atom.

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THE CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
SCIENCE COLLEGE,
BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY,
BANARAS-5.

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